

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF THREE-DIMENSIONAL

WOVEN FIBER COMPOSITES

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Summary

Woven fiber materials are gaining increasing technological importance as reinforcements for polymeric, metal, and ceramic matrix composites. In the case of two-dimensional woven fabric composites, a significant effort has been made by the authors in investigating the relation between fabric structure and properties. They identified the various types of weaves by the material and geometrical patterns of repeats as well as the size of yarns. Analytical models for analyzing the thermo-mechanical properties including the nonlinear stress-strain behavior also have been established.

The structure and properties of three-dimensional (3-D) woven fiber composites have recently been described by several authors. These composites with multi-directional reinforcements are fabricated by a weaving or braiding technique. In comparing with two-dimensional (2-D) composites based upon fabrics or unidirectional tapes, 3-D composites can be produced with considerable flexibility in their sizes along the length, width and thickness directions. The integral nature of these composites provides improved stiffness and strength in the thickness direction, along which interlaminar failure often occurs in 2-D composites.

This paper reports the recent advances in the analytical and experimental studies of 3-D composites. In the analytical aspect, two techniques based upon strain energy consideration and a modified laminated plate theory have been developed to model the constitutive relations of 3-D fabric composites in general. In the experimental aspects, 3-D braided composites of FP fiber in an aluminum matrix are adopted. Characterization of tensile, compressive and shear properties and metallographic investigations have been performed. The results are correlated with theoretical analyses.

Introduction

The new advances in composite fabrication technology have resulted in a revival of interest in the woven fabric composites. Some of the characteristics of the fabric composites that make them attractive materials for structural applications are their low fabrication cost, formability to complex shapes and ease of manufacture of large structural components.

The elastic properties and strength of the 2-D biaxial and triaxial woven fabric composites have been extensively studied during the past few years by Ishikawa, Chou and co-workers (1-7). While the 2-D fabric composites offer the above economic and technological advantages, like the conventional composites they have very poor through-the-thickness properties. Therefore, their use is limited in applications where fatigue and impact resistance are critical requirements.

The 3-D fabric composites provide great improvement in the properties along the thickness direction. However, until recently most of the 3-D woven fabrics were orthogonal weaves whose fabrication is not only expensive but also complex and offers little feasibility for automation.

The recently developed 3-D braided composites (8-11) provide most of the advantages of the conventional woven fabric composites plus additional unique characteristics including a fully integrated nature and the possibility of design and manufacture with the aid of a computer. 3-D braided structures have been successfully made with a wide range of fiber reinforcements in polymeric, metal, or ceramic matrix materials, and in a variety of shapes and sizes.

The thermoelastic properties of 3-D braided fiber composites have recently been investigated by Ma, Yang and Chou (12-16) for the case where both fiber and matrix are linearly elastic. They used two analytical methods. In the first method which is based on an energy approach (12), the composite structure is assumed to be represented by the unit cell shown in Fig. 1. The unit cell is centered around an "interlock" of yarns that occupy positions along the edges and the diagonals of the parallel piped. Each yarn is regarded as a "composite rod" and the properties of the composite are derived from the 3-D composite rod structure. The dimensions, p_a , p_b and p_c , of the unit cell are determined by the weaving pattern used. Strain energies of the unit cell due to yarn axial tension, bending and lateral compression at the interlock have been taken into account. The effective composite elastic constants are derived by the application of an energy principle.

The second method used by Chou and co-workers to derive the elastic properties of the 3-D braided composites is based on a "fiber inclination" model (13). The unit cell, shown in Fig. 2, is constructed by assuming fiber bundles oriented in four diagonal directions in a rectangular parallelepiped. The unit cell is treated as an assemblage of four inclined laminae. The classical laminated plate theory is then applied to analyze the effective elastic moduli of the composite unit cell.

The purposes of this study were to characterize the basic mechanical properties of the new 3-D braided FP/Al-Li composites, to identify their failure mechanisms under various loading conditions, and to correlate their measured elastic properties with the predictions of the models presented above.

Fig. 1. Composite unit cell for the analysis of the elastic moduli of 3-D braided composites by Chou et al using an energy approach (12).

Fig. 2. Composite unit cell for the "Fiber Inclination Model" used by Chou et al (13).

Experimental Procedures

Material

3-D braided composites of FP fiber in an aluminum-lithium matrix were used for the experimental studies. FP fiber is a continuous, polycrystalline α -alumina filament manufactured by E. I. DuPont Co. The suggested properties of this fiber are given in Table I (17). Each fiber yarn contains 210 filaments with circular cross sections of approximately 20 μ m diameter. To facilitate wetting, the aluminum matrix is alloyed with between 2 to 3 wt% lithium which is a highly reactive material. This provides a very strong chemical bond between the fiber and the matrix.

Table I. Properties of Fiber FP(17)

Tensile strength	: 1380 MPa (200 ksi)
Tensile modulus	: 345-379 GPa (50-55 Mpsi)
Elongation	: 0.4%
Density	: 3.90 g/cm ³ .
Specific strength	: 3.56x10 ⁶ cm
Specific modulus	: 8.89x10 ⁸ cm
Melting point	: 2045 ^o C

The 3-D braided preforms were prepared by Dr. Frank Ko at Drexel University, Philadelphia, Pa., using the Magnaweave procedure. Details of this procedure are given in References (8-11). The preforms had a (1x1x3) braid structure with a braiding angle of about 20^o. Each fiber bundle contained 10 yarns. Each preform was fabricated to the size of the final specimen along the width and thickness directions. The preforms were impregnated with the Al-Li alloy by E. I. DuPont Co., using a liquid metal vacuum infiltration technique. The resulting composite specimens, therefore, had a fully integrated fiber structure.

The fiber content in the composite, V_f , was only 17%; this, obviously, is much below the range of V_f where composites are effective reinforcing materials. However, it should be pointed out that this has been the first batch of the braided FP/Al-Li manufactured and, therefore, some material inadequacies were to be expected. As the fabrication technology develops, many of the processing parameters are optimized and brought under control. In addition to the low V_f , specimens had other anomalies such as internal flaws due to insufficient impregnation of fibers, as detected by ultrasonic C-scan inspection, and a relatively thick surface layer of unreinforced aluminum alloy on one face of the composite panels.

Tensile Tests

Tensile tests were conducted along the axial direction on parallel sided specimens of 203mm x 25mm x 6.3mm (8in x 1in x 0.25in) dimensions. The specimen ends were reinforced with 38mm long by 3mm thick aluminum tabs using the Eccobond 45 epoxy adhesive manufactured by Emerson and Cuming, Inc. Electrical resistance strain gauges were mounted at the center of each

specimen on either side along the 0° and 90° directions and strain was measured throughout the test by means of a multichannel Daytronic strain recorder. Tests were carried out on an Instron TT-D universal testing machine at a cross head speed of 0.02mm/s (0.05 in/min)

To obtain additional information about the onset and perhaps the mechanism of failure, acoustic emission (AE) data was also collected during the tensile tests using a 2-channel Physical Acoustics Corporation (PAC) 3000/3004 system. In order to block out noise generated at the grips, two "guard" sensors were attached to the specimen ends in addition to the main sensor which was positioned at mid-length. The main sensor was connected to one of the two channels on the AE system and the two guard sensors were both connected to the other channel via a BNC connector. The program was then set to reject any signals coming from the guard sensors and only accept signals arrived at the main sensor. The total system gain was adjusted to 80db on each channel and the threshold voltage was set to 1.0 volt.

A total of four specimens were tested to failure with AE data being obtained on only two of them. In addition to the composite specimens, tensile tests were also carried out on specimens of the neat Al-Li matrix alloy in the as-cast condition. Rectangular filleted specimens were prepared in accordance with the ASTM B 557M standard method for tensile testing of aluminum alloys (18). These were 3mm (0.125in) thick and 152mm (6 in) long with a gauge length of 70mm. The width of specimens within the grip section was 12.7mm (0.5in) and that in the reduced area was 9.5mm (0.375 in).

Compression Tests

Attempts to measure the compressive strength of the FP/Al-Li composites using parallel sided, rectangular specimens with aluminum end tabs failed due to the shear failure of the adhesive bond within the grip region at almost half the expected compressive failure load. Therefore, it became necessary to reduce the specimen width within the gauge section at the expense of the integrated nature of the fiber structure. This filleting not only creates the undesirable fiber ends but, also, may induce damage from the machining operation. Therefore, the compressive strength measured on these specimens may well be quite lower than the actual strength of the 3-D integrated structure.

Compression specimens were 6.3mm (0.25in) thick with a total length of 152mm (6in) and a gauge length of 12.7mm (0.5in). The ends were reinforced with 63mm long by 3mm thick aluminum tabs. The width of specimens within the reduced section was 6.3mm and that in the grip region was 12.7mm. Electrical resistance strain gauges were bonded to both surfaces of each specimen along the 0° and 90° directions for strain measurements. Tests were performed with the IITRI (Illinois Institute of Technology Research Institute) compression fixture (19), shown in Fig. 3, on a 10,000 Kgf Model 1324 Instron testing machine at a cross head speed of 0.02mm/s (0.05in/min). A total of three specimens were tested to failure and stress-strain curves were obtained for each.

Shear Tests

Four different shear tests were tried in order to measure the in-plane (intralaminar) and the interlaminar shear properties of the composite specimens. In the short beam shear test (20), premature failure always occurred by a flexural mode on the tensile surface of the specimen even

though a very short specimen with a span to depth ratio of only 3 was used. This was due to the high ratio of the interlaminar shear strength to tensile strength in the 3-D braided FP/Al-Li composites. The two-rail shear test (21) also proved inadequate, always ending with the failure of material around the holes where the rails were bolted to the composite. Applying 24mm wide steel doublers to the rail area on the specimen resulted in an almost doubling of the limiting failure load but did not entirely eliminate the problem.

The other two shear tests were more successful. These were the Iosipescu shear test originally proposed by Iosipescu (22) for isotropic materials and applied to composite laminates by Walrath and Adams (23,24), and the double-notch shear test specified in the ASTM D3846 method (25).

The Iosipescu test was used to measure the in-plane shear properties. Schematic drawings of the specimen and loading fixture are given in Fig. 4. A state of pure shear is achieved in the small region between the two notches when a compressive load is applied to the two halves of the specimen. It is suggested that shear strain can be measured within the region of pure shear by applying strain gauges along the $\pm 45^\circ$ directions to the loading axis. This has been done successfully for a range of composite laminates.

The Iosipescu shear specimens had a thickness of 6.3mm (0.25in) and were made with two types of notches: the standard notch shown in Fig. 4(a) and a blunt notch shown in Fig. 4(b). The blunt notch has recently been recommended by Walrath and Adams (24) in order to reduce the stress concentration at the tip of the notch and to achieve a more uniform state of stress in the area between the notches in a composite material. Specimens were prepared along directions both parallel and perpendicular to the braiding axis. $\pm 45^\circ$ strain gauge rosettes were affixed to both surfaces of each specimen at midway between the notches. Compressive load was applied by a Model 1324 Instron testing machine at a cross head speed of 0.02mm/s. At least three specimens were tested in each orientation and the in-plane shear strength, S_{xy} , was calculated from the following equation:

$$S_{xy} = \frac{P_F}{D \cdot T}$$

where P_F is the compressive load at failure and D and T are the distance between the notch tips and the specimen thickness, respectively.

The interlaminar shear strength was measured by the double-notch shear test method. The specimen geometry and the fixture are given in Fig. 5. A compressive load was applied to the specimen at a cross head speed of 0.02mm/s until failure occurred by shear on the plane between the two notches. The interlaminar shear strength S_{xz} was then calculated from the equation below:

$$S_{xz} = \frac{P_F}{W \cdot D}$$

W and D are the width and the notch spacing in the specimen, respectively. A total of four specimens were tested.

The disadvantage of both the Iosipescu and the double-notched shear tests is that specimens require machining which may result in reduced strength measurements as already discussed.

Fig. 3. ITTRI Compression fixture and specimen geometry.

Fig. 4. Schematics of the Iosipescu specimen with a (a) standard notch and (b) blunt notch, and (c) the loading fixture.

Microscopy

After failure, the tension, compression, and shear specimens were sectioned by a liquid-cooled rotary diamond saw and prepared for fractography and failure analyses by a scanning electron microscope (SEM) and conventional optical microscope. The SEM specimens were coated with a thin layer of gold to enhance their electrical conductivity. Specimens for optical microscopy were mounted in a polymer, then ground and polished down to 1 μ m with diamond paste under low applied pressure to prevent fiber breakage.

Results

Tensile Behavior

Fig. 6 depicts a typical tensile stress-strain curve for the neat Al-Li matrix. The properties measured included a Young's modulus of 73 GPa (10.6 \times 10¹⁰ Psi), an ultimate strength of 154 MPa (22.3 Ksi). A 0.2% yield strength of 83MPa (12 Ksi) and an elongation of 11%.

The composite material showed strength and stiffness values that were only slightly higher than those of the unreinforced matrix as was expected because of the very low V_F (~17%). The ultimate strength was 189 MPa and the initial Young's Modulus equalled 97GPa. The stress-strain curve, given in Fig. 7(a), showed a bilinear behavior with the "knee" occurring at a strain of about 0.02%. The secondary Young's Modulus was 61GPa. Fig. 7 also shows the acoustic emission count and amplitude data obtained during the tensile tests. There were small bursts of AE starting at a strain almost coinciding with the "knee" in the stress-strain curve. However, the rapid increase in the AE counts did not occur until a strain of about 0.17% was reached and continued until the final failure. The AE amplitude distribution data shown in Fig. 7(b) and the event duration data indicated that most of the AE events were of medium to high amplitude and relatively short duration, normally typical of matrix shear failure or fiber fracture.

All tensile specimens fractured in a plane perpendicular to the loading axis and within the gauge length. Examination of the location of failure and its correlation with ultrasonic C-scan mappings obtained prior to the tests revealed that in at least one sample, final failure was associated with a pre-existing flaw in the material structure and the sample failed at a stress lower than the average value reported above.

The fracture surface had the appearance of a ductile fracture with many dimples. SEM examinations of the fracture surface revealed brittle fracture of fibers and considerable deformation in the matrix between the fibers (Fig. 8). Almost no fiber pullout was detected. Optical microscopy inspections of the above specimens showed multiple fracture of fibers near the plane of the crack with an average crack spacing of approximately 120 μ m (Fig. 9). There were only a few isolated fiber fractures at large distances away from the plane of the crack.

Compressive Behavior

The average values of the ultimate compressive strength and the initial Young's modulus measured for the braided FP/Al composite were 838 Mpa 106GPa respectively. A typical compressive stress-strain curve is shown in Fig. 10. The curve demonstrated an initial linear region up to a strain of

Fig. 5. The double-notch shear test specimen and loading fixture.

Fig. 6. The initial part of the tensile stress-strain curve obtained for the Al-3%Li matrix material.

Fig. 7. (a) The tensile stress-strain curve with AE count data and (b) AE amplitude distribution for 3-D braided FP/A&Li composite.

about 0.15% followed by a non-linear behavior. Other compressive properties included a failure strain of about 1.8% and a major Poisson's ratio of 0.3.

Kinking appeared to be the primary mode of failure in compression. Kinks were formed on all four surfaces of specimens and were preceded by longitudinal cracks. A side view of a specimen that was mounted and polished after failure to show kinking is depicted in Fig. 11. Microscopic examinations of failure revealed that fibers had broken into numerous fragments within the kinked region. This observation correlates with that for unidirectional FP/Al-Li composites by Shetty and Chou (26).

Shear Behavior

The in-plane shear strength, S_{xy} , of the composite was measured with the Iosipescu shear test. Initial experiments in which standard specimens with a sharp, 90° V-notch were used gave shear strengths of 109MPa parallel and 115MPa perpendicular to the braiding axis. Theoretically, these two shear strengths i.e., S_{xy} and S_{yx} , should be the same.

In the experiments that followed, the standard V-notch was replaced by a blunt notch with a tip radius of 0.64mm and an angle of 100° in order to reduce stress concentrations at the tip of the notch. These tests yielded a shear strength of ~138MPa parallel to the braiding direction; an improvement of almost 25% over the values obtained from the standard notch. No measurements were made in the perpendicular direction due to the material depletion.

Although $\pm 45^\circ$ strain gauge rosettes were carefully bonded to both sides of each specimen as recommended in the test procedure, no consistent strain reading could be obtained on any of the specimens. This was possibly due to the relatively small size of the region of pure shear, and therefore, the small size of the strain gauge used (1.6mm long), with respect to the highly nonhomogeneous and coarse 3-D braided structure with a relatively large bundle size. Hence, it was not possible to measure meaningful values for the shear modulus.

All Iosipescu specimens broke on a single plane between the tips of the two notches in a shear mode of failure. SEM fractographs of specimens in parallel and perpendicular directions are shown in Fig. 12.

The interlaminar shear strength of the braided composite was measured by the double-notched shear test described earlier. Specimens failed by shear on the plane between the two notches under the applied compressive load. The interlaminar shear strength was about 141MPa.

Discussion

An objective discussion of the properties of 3-D braided FP/Al-Li composites as compared with conventional laminates based on the present findings is somewhat difficult because of the low fiber content of the material tested. Most of the experimental data available for unidirectional FP/Al-Li composites are in the range of V_f between 35 to 55% (16,26,27). As already pointed out, the 3-D material prepared for this study was largely experimental in which the processing parameters were difficult to control. The fabrication technique has since been refined and currently specimens with a fiber volume fraction of 35 to 40% are being

Fig. 8. SEM fractograph of specimen failed in tension. Note the brittle fracture of fibers and plastic deformation in the matrix.

Fig. 9. Multiple cracking of fibers under tensile loading in a region near the plane of fracture.

Fig. 10. The compressive stress-strain curve obtained for the 3-D braided FP/Al-Li composite.

Fig. 11. Side view of specimen failed under compressive loading, showing the "Kinking" mode of failure.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 12. SEM Fractographs of Iosipescu shear specimens showing the shear failure modes for (a) perpendicular and (b) parallel directions to the loading axis.

manufactured and test results will be reported in the near future. Nevertheless, some useful conclusions can be derived from this work that may lay a basis for future studies.

In Table II, the mechanical properties of the 3-D braided composite measured in this work are listed and the elastic moduli are compared with the theoretical predictions based upon the model of Chou and co-workers (12). For the sake of comparison, theoretical properties of a $\pm 20^\circ$ angle ply and a 0° unidirectional FP/Al-Li laminate with a V_f of 17% are also listed. The tensile strength of the unidirectional composite is calculated from the simple rule of mixtures, the shear strengths are based on the equations given by Chamis (28) and the compressive strength is derived from the following equation by Rosen and Co-workers (29) for the case of fiber microbuckling against a plastic matrix,

$$\sigma_{uc} = \left[\frac{E_f \cdot V_f \cdot \sigma_{ym}}{3(1-V_f)} \right]^{1/2}$$

Pattnaik, Kozcak and Rogers (30) and Shetty and Chou (25) have studied the compressive failure of unidirectional FP/Al composites under axial loading and found that kinking due to local fiber microbuckling was the prevalent mode of failure. Fiber microbuckling occurs largely due to local inhomogenieties, stress concentrations and fiber misalignment in the material. Their work also showed that while the above equation gave more reasonable strength values than other theories for compressive strength, its predictions were still considerably higher than values measured. In their calculations, Pattnaik et al used a matrix yield stress, σ_{ym} , of 193MPa (25Ksi) while the compressive strength in Table II is based on a σ_{ym} of 83MPa (12Ksi) as measured in the present work. The 3-D braided composites also failed in compression by a complex kinking mode as shown in Fig. 11.

Comparison of the braided composite with the unidirectional laminate given in Table II shows that while the tensile and compressive properties suffer in the 3-D braided structure as is the case for any off-axis laminate, the shear properties greatly benefit from such a fiber construction. The behavior of the braided composite with the braid angle of 20° appears to be relatively close to that of a $\pm 20^\circ$ angle-ply laminate except for the interlaminar shear strength where a much higher value is achieved in the braided composite. This improved interlaminar shear and tensile properties in the thickness direction has been the main incentive in the development of the 3-D braided composites and because of it, the 3-D structure is expected to have much improved fracture, fatigue and drop-weight impact resistance over the conventional laminates. The fracture and impact resistance of the FP/Al-Li braided composites are currently being investigated.

Table II also indicates that there is a good correlation between experimental values of the material elastic moduli and Poisson's ratios with theoretical predictions of Chou et al (12). The slightly higher theoretical values could be, at least in part, due to the fact that the fiber properties reported in Table I and used for these calculations have been measured on perfect, virgin fibers and they, therefore, represent an upper limit for the in-situ fiber properties. Calculating the fiber properties from those measured on unidirectional composites (17,27) gave values of 1075MPa (156Ksi) for the tensile strength and 330 GPa (50×10^6 Psi) for the tensile modulus; both significantly lower than those reported in Table I.

While fibers are weaker in the composite, the in-situ strength of the

Table II. Mechanical Properties of FP/Al-Li Composites
 $V_f = 17\%$

<u>Property</u>	<u>Unit</u>	<u>3-D Braided</u>		<u>±20° Angle Ply</u>	<u>0° Unidirectional</u>
		(Experimental)	(Theoretical)	(Theoretical)	(Theoretical)
<u>Tensile</u>					
Ultimate Strength	MPa(Ksi)	189(27)	--	281.3(30)	307.7(43.96)
Initial Young's Modulus	GPa(Msi)	97(13.9)	115.6(16.5)	114.3(16.3)	135 (19.3)
Poisson's Ratio	--	0.33	0.33	0.36	0.31

<u>Compressive</u>					
Ultimate Strength	MPa(Ksi)	837.6(119.6)	--	--	1,482(211.7)
Initial Young's Modulus	GPa(Msi)	106 (15.2)	115.6(16.5)	114.3(16.3)	135(19.3)
Poisson's Ratio	--	0.3	0.33	0.36	0.31

<u>Shear</u>					
In-Plane Shear Strength	MPa(Ksi)	139.6(19.9)	--	151.20(21.6)	100.8(14.4)
In-Plane Shear Modulus	GPa(Msi)	--	37.4(5.3)	42.3 (6.0)	32.5(4.6)
Interlaminar Shear Strength	MPa (Msi)	144.5(20.5)	--	--	100.8(14.4)

matrix may well be higher than that measured for the bulk material. Such a phenomenon has been observed by some investigators (31,32) and discussed by Kelly (33). Briefly, when the fiber spacing is very small (about 10 μ m or less), as is the case within the fiber bundles in the material tested (Fig. 9), the yield stress of the matrix will be controlled by the Orowan stress and it is higher than that of the bulk matrix. The yield stress and work hardening both increase with decreasing the spacing between fibers. While the yield stress goes up, the strain at which the matrix starts yielding in the composite drops for very small fiber spacings (about 1 μ m). Yielding of the matrix appears to be responsible for the bilinearity in the stress-strain curve shown in Fig. 7. The bilinear behavior has also been observed in the unidirectional FP/Al-Li composites (17,26,27) and is therefore believed to be a material property rather than an effect caused by the braided structure. If it is assumed that the contribution of the matrix after its yielding to the composite modulus is negligible, the Young's modulus of the unidirectional composite can then be calculated from $E_c = V_f E_f$. This equation yields a value of 65 GPa which is slightly higher than the secondary modulus of 61 GPa measured for the braided composite.

Because of the highly inhomogeneous microstructure of the braided composite in which fiber bundles maintain their identity, the fiber volume fraction within the bundle, V_{fb} , is much higher than the average V_f of the composite. Therefore, any analytical treatment of the failure mechanism and strength should include an analysis of strength within the densely packed bundles and one at the composite level where a fiber bundle may be treated as a single filament whose properties are those of a composite with a V_f equal to V_{fb} .

The theories of single and multiple fracture (33,34) predict that in the unidirectional FP/Al composite, multiple fiber fracture is the prevailing mode of failure at V_f values less than about 7%. At higher values of V_f , single fracture becomes predominant. For braided composites, if the strength is assumed to follow the simple model given by Ko (11), the fiber volume fraction $(V_f)_{max}$ at which the transition from the multiple to single fracture occurs can be derived from the following equation.

$$(V_f)_{max} = \frac{\sigma_{um} - \sigma'_m}{\sigma_{uf} \cos^2 \theta + (\sigma_{um} - \sigma'_m)}$$

where σ'_m is the stress on the matrix at the failure strain of the fibers and θ is the braid angle. Using the matrix properties measured in this work and a σ_{uf} value of 1075 MPa yields a $(V_f)_{max}$ of about 10% for the braided composite. Therefore, failure of the composite material tested would still be by a single fracture in which failure of one bundle triggers the fracture of the adjacent bundles until all fiber bundles are broken. Because of the very high load carried by the fiber bundles, the matrix material bridging the broken bundles will not be able to withstand the loads thrown onto it and it too will fail. This results in a composite failure strain equal to that of the fiber bundle as observed in this study. Within each bundle, also, a single fracture mode rules. This failure mechanism can account for the dimpled appearance of the fracture surface observed in this material under tensile loads. The multiple fracture of fibers near the plane of the crack could be due to the complex state of stress ahead of the advancing crack, and fiber bending or because of the low V_f of composite which may position it in a borderline situation where some multiple fracture could occur within the bundles. The acoustic emission data showed that failure at microstructural level initiates at a strain of 0.17%.

The AE events are mostly of medium to high amplitude which usually apply to fiber fracture.

Conclusions

The following conclusions can be derived from this investigation:

1. The experimental Young's moduli and the Poisson's ratios of the 3-D braided FP/Al-Li composite showed a good agreement with the theoretical predictions of Chou, et al based on an energy approach.
2. The braided composite with braiding angle of 20° appeared to show tensile, compression and in-plane shear properties that were only slightly lower than those predicted for a $\pm 20^{\circ}$ angle-ply laminate. However, the interlaminar shear strength of the 3-D structure was considerably higher than that expected for the angle-ply laminate.
3. Under tensile loading, the braided FP/Al-Li composite failed by a single fracture mode at the bundle level with some multiple cracking of fibers observed near the plane of the fracture. The acoustic emission data indicated that the onset of microstructural failure was at 0.17%. In compression, failure was predominantly by kinking.
4. In the area of experimental mechanics, new tests need to be developed or the existing methods modified particularly for the shear behavior of the metal matrix braided composites. Machining of specimens should be avoided as much as possible because it destroys the integrated nature of the material and thus results in lower measurements of strength.

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